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Classification of Malware Attack using Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract : This paper deals with the classification of malware attacks using Machine Learning into nine different families: Ramnit, Lollipop, Kelihos_ver3, Vundo, Simda, Tracur, Kelihos_ver1, Obfuscator.ACY, Gatak. Due to the rapid growth of targeted malware attacks, malware analysis and family classification are important. There are numerous types of malware that can affect a system to differing degrees, making it a complex and ever-evolving threat. The feature extraction phase is used to choose and transform the raw data into a collection of valuable features that can be used to train a machine learning model. As we try feature extraction methods, calculating file size and n-gram sequences and selecting the top feature by using SelectKBest and the chi-squared test. We have proposed a supervised machine learning algorithm. Here particularly K-Nearest Neighbor, Random Forest, and XGBoost have been used. Based on how closely new malware samples resemble previously classified samples, the K-Nearest Neighbor algorithm can classify them into already identified families. By choosing randomly from subsets of features and data for each decision tree, Random Forest combines the forecasts of all the trees. The gradient boosting method used by XGBoost involves building new trees while incorporating the mistakes of the prior trees.

Keywords: File Size, Unigram, Bigram, Trigram, Malware attack, K-Nearest Neighbor, Random Forest, XGBoost, Log-Loss

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Malware Attack

A malware attack is defined as the unauthorized intrusion of harmful software into a computer system or network with the aim of interfering with operations, causing harm, or gaining unauthorized access to confidential data. A broad category of malicious software known as malware includes viruses, worms, Trojan horses, ransomware, spyware, and adware [11].

In our datasets, we have nine families as follows:

- i). Ramnit: It is a computer worm that spreads through infected files, portable drives, and network shares that target Windows operating systems. It is renowned for stealing private data, including login credentials and banking information.
- ii) Lollipop: An Android device is often infected by Lollipop through malicious apps or websites. It can carry out a number of dangerous actions, such as collecting personal information and presenting intrusive adverts, by disguising itself as genuine applications.
- iii) Kelihos_ver3: It is predominantly targeted Windows-based systems. It is intended to build a network of compromised machines that fraudsters can remotely manage and use

to carry out different nefarious tasks, such as sending spam emails and spreading more malware.

iv)Vundo: A Trojan that affects Windows-based computers, Vundo is sometimes referred to as VirtuMonde. It is frequently offered in bundles with other applications or spread through malicious websites.

v)Simda: It is a botnet malware that primarily spreads through email attachments, rogue websites, and exploit kits. Once infected, it enables attackers to take advantage of vulnerable systems and exploit them for a variety of nefarious tasks, like sending spam emails or launching additional attacks.

vi)Tracur: It mostly targets Windows-based computers. It is renowned for sending visitors to dangerous content, such as phishing websites and false antivirus scams, and often spreads through malicious websites or legitimate websites that have been hijacked.

vii)Kelihos_ver1: It mostly targets Windows-based computers. It is made to send spam emails, disseminate malware, and carry out other nefarious deeds, frequently using email-based campaigns.

viii)Obfuscator.ACY: It is a form of malware obfuscation technique, to conceal the true nature and intent of their malicious code. It alters the code to make it more difficult for security software to analyze and detect.

ix)Gatak: It is a Trojan that mostly targets Windows-based computers. It is frequently spread by malicious email attachments or exploit kits and is well recognized for its information-stealing skills, focusing in particular on login credentials and sensitive data.

1.2. Machine Learning

In Machine Learning, we are creating algorithms and models that allow computers to learn and make predictions or judgments without being explicitly programmed and it is a subset of artificial intelligence. It focuses on creating systems that can analyze data and learn from experience to automatically enhance performance [12]. Types of machine learning:

1. Supervised learning- With supervised learning, we train a model with labeled data in order to understand the relationship between input data and their corresponding labels. The goal is to develop a model that, using the patterns it has discovered from the labeled training data, can correctly predict or categorize new, unobserved data [13].
2. Unsupervised learning- It is a branch of machine learning where we work with data that has no existing labels or known patterns. We can examine the data and find hidden patterns, connections, or clusters using unsupervised learning methods. The objective is to extract significant insights and beneficial information from the data itself [13].
3. Reinforcement learning - It involves creating an agent—a system that learns to perform better through interactions with its surroundings. A reward signal that offers feedback on the agent's behavior is given to it along with information about the environment's current state. The agent asks to identify a set of activities that

maximize the earned rewards by studying various acts and their effects or by making conscious choices.[13]

1.3. Log-Loss

For the performance metrics, we have used the log-loss function. A classification model's performance can be evaluated using the evaluation data known as log loss. It determines the difference between expected probability and actual labels; smaller values indicate a more accurate prediction. The Log Loss for a perfect model would be 0. The difference between expected probability and actual outcomes can be measured using Log Loss, which, unlike accuracy, which counts successful predictions, takes into consideration the uncertainty of predicted labels by comparing them to the actual labeling [10].

The visualization of Machine Learning-based Classification into 9 Malware Families is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Malware Classification Pipeline

The subsequent phases of the research are outlined as follows: Section 2 comprises the Related Work. Section 3 provides an extensive analysis of the various methodologies. Section 4 provides a comprehensive assessment of the proposed framework, including an in-depth analysis of model

selection, experimental conditions, and the recommended approach. Section 5 conducts a comparative analysis based on the findings. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

In machine learning and data analysis activities, feature extraction is vital. It includes identifying and extracting the most important features, patterns, or correlations from raw data so that they can be utilized to train models and carry out the classification of malware families. As we try feature extraction methods, calculating file size of ASM file and Byte file, extraction unigram feature extraction of ASM file and Byte file, extracting bigram feature extraction using ASM file and Byte file as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively and extracting trigram feature extraction using ASM file.

Calculating the file size ASM file and byte file is calculated by using 'statinfo.st_size' and converting the file size into megabytes by dividing the calculated file by 1024*1024 and adding their class labels after checking if the filename is present in the classLable.csv file or not.

	ID	size	Class
0	02I0CvYEy8mjuiAQHax3	0.792969	6
1	02m1BLHZTDFXGa7Nt6cr	0.594727	6
2	03nJaQV6K20bICUmyWoR	1.996582	6
3	04mcPSei852tgIKUwTJr	0.594727	9
4	05LHG8fR3iPn6agIo9z7	2.817871	6
...
1996	ljuryB4bfagHqV5FM9Ae	2.223145	4
1997	lLvracbzqACpwsUtnuHh	0.835449	4
1998	LNAnljesrEDma5oUfVZI	2.223145	4
1999	loIP1tiwELF9YNZQjsUO	2.223145	4
2000	LOqA6FX02GwguYrI1Zbe	0.254883	4

[2001 rows x 3 columns]

Figure 2: File Size of Byte File

	ID	size	Class
0	02I0CvYEy8mjuiAQHax3	3.296968	6
1	02m1BLHZTDFXGa7Nt6cr	1.035177	6
2	03nJaQV6K20bICUmyWoR	5.214187	6
3	04mcPSei852tgIKUwTJr	1.175122	9
4	05LHG8fR3iPn6agIo9z7	6.637392	6
...
1996	ljuryB4bfagHqV5FM9Ae	11.279039	4
1997	lLvracbzqACpwsUtnuHh	4.547873	4
1998	LNAnljesrEDma5oUfVZI	10.955087	4
1999	loIP1tiwELF9YNZQjsUO	11.269457	4
2000	LOqA6FX02GwguYrI1Zbe	1.957262	4

[2001 rows x 3 columns]

Figure 3: File Size of ASM file

Unigram analyzes the set of single characters or bytes. Unigram feature extraction of Byte files is shown in Figure 4, we are firstly converting the byte files into a text file and removing the address from each line from a text file and it iterates over each text file and read each line and count the frequency for each of the bytes. And for the unigram feature extraction of the ASM file as shown in Figure 5, we are first converting the asm file into a text file and making the vocabulary which contains the list of opcodes, prefixes, registers, and keywords.

The opcodes list contains common assembly language instructions such as jmp, mov, cmp, call, push, pop, xor, add, sub, test, rol, ror. The prefixes list contains the prefixes that modify instructions or data in memory such as db, dw, dd, dq, rel, abs, lock, rep. The `keywords` list contains keywords such as section, global, extern, align, lea, ret. The `registers` list contains the CPU registers such as edx, esi, eax, ebx, ecx, edi, ebp, esp, cr0, cr2, cr3, cr4, xmm0, xmm1, xmm2, xmm3. Create a countVectorizer using this vocabulary for finding the frequency count for each vocabulary. countVectorizer is used to convert text into numerical data [6].

Out[14]:

	ID	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	...	f7	f8	f9	fa	fb	fc	fd	fe	ff	??
0	02iOCvYEy8mjiuAQHax3	85090	414	340	331	350	324	303	299	327	...	317	305	295	333	344	325	332	321	403	60984
1	02mIBLHZTDFXGa7Ni6cr	33141	430	311	410	411	330	385	863	345	...	425	333	312	272	279	295	300	334	12186	25362
2	03nJaQV6K2ObiCUmyWoR	12369	2317	2111	2210	2087	2120	2106	2186	2424	...	3048	2001	2056	1977	2086	2223	2019	2025	3193	16272
3	04mcPSei852tqjKUwTJr	33759	1467	946	673	1476	1027	923	654	1468	...	430	827	388	407	473	720	558	921	5900	388
4	05LHG8fR3iPn6agj0z7	172538	3489	2653	3551	2569	2667	2390	2277	2058	...	2247	2056	2119	1960	2050	1943	2138	1969	64831	21260
...
1996	ljyB4bfa9HqV5FM9Ae	5165	1159	1111	1198	1248	1107	1129	1047	1111	...	1180	1146	1173	1106	1107	1108	1099	1104	1266	347348
1997	lLvracbzqACpwsUtnuHh	5710	538	492	680	555	491	502	484	516	...	495	487	464	451	488	431	478	462	560	109188
1998	LNAnijesfEDma5oUfVZI	4057	1269	1205	1292	1191	1153	1133	1140	1168	...	1198	1240	1118	1214	1202	1110	1156	1201	1188	339488
1999	loiPtiwELF9YNZQJSUO	5268	1177	1072	1222	1238	1159	1143	1126	1149	...	1218	1125	1094	1154	1088	1113	1114	1107	1178	347816
2000	LOqAGFX02GWguYi11Zbe	5671	221	270	323	313	155	248	147	261	...	191	248	159	247	163	249	149	226	231	11396

2001 rows x 258 columns

Figure 4: Unigram feature of Byte file

Out[25]:

	ID	jmp	mov	cmp	call	push	pop	xor	add	sub	...	ebp	esp	cr0	cr2	cr3	cr4	xmm0	xmm1	xmm2	xmm3
0	02IOCvYEy8mjuAQHax3	39	15	2	3	23	13	10	12	7	...	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	02mBLHZTDFXGa7N6cr	36	291	46	55	184	59	65	122	66	...	27	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	03nJaQV6K2ObICUmyWoR	108	589	118	64	419	193	167	169	157	...	123	110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	04mcPSei852tgIKUwTJr	1	45	154	134	489	203	72	74	165	...	38	42	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	05LHG8fR3IPn6aglo9z7	799	705	125	73	365	183	154	436	160	...	115	90	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
...
1996	ljuryB4bfagHqV5FM9Ae	5	198	56	97	372	148	73	137	54	...	27	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1997	lVracbzqACpwsUtnuHh	87	104	34	29	210	80	43	79	23	...	22	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1998	LNAnljesrEDma5oUJVZI	329	262	72	87	420	143	61	129	97	...	62	57	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1999	lolP1tiwELF9YNZQJSUO	2	152	39	91	284	128	53	126	46	...	18	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2000	LQqA6FX02GWguYr1Zbe	149	134	45	35	248	97	23	71	21	...	64	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

2001 rows x 43 columns

Figure 5: Unigram feature of ASM file

Bigram analyzes the set of two characters or bytes [7]. Bigram feature extraction of Byte files creates the countVectorizer for bigram and finds the frequency for each of the pair of bytes and selects the top 2000 important features from the bigram feature using SelectKBest and chi-squared test as shown in Figure 6. SelectKBest is the method for selecting the K highest feature based on the score, for the scoring function chi-squared test is used [8]. The chi-squared test is the statistical test that is used to measure the difference between observed results and expected results and find the relation between them [9]. And in the ASM file, it makes the two pairs of vocabulary using countVectorizer and finds the frequency of each of the pairs, and selects the top 500 important features as shown in Figure 7 from the bigram feature using SelectKBest and chi-squared test.

Out[22]:

	ID	?? ff	cc cb	ff fe	f0 ef	fe ??	00 fe	10 0f	69 68	b5 b4	...	8b d0	05 13	00 23	21 ??	0f a0	a1 a0	c7 05	8b c5	0f 6c	03 06
0	02IOCvYEy8mjuAQHax3	0	2	5	2	0	1	0	0	3	...	3	2	5	0	2	0	1	2	4	2
1	02mBLHZTDFXGa7N6cr	0	2	21	5	0	48	7	0	2	...	3	2	45	0	0	1	0	0	1	1
2	03nJaQV6K2ObICUmyWoR	0	9	24	7	0	11	6	4	8	...	8	11	10	0	9	8	10	12	11	11
3	04mcPSei852tgIKUwTJr	0	0	22	2	0	74	4	0	1	...	6	0	45	0	1	0	9	5	1	0
4	05LHG8fR3IPn6aglo9z7	0	3	133	8	0	229	9	7	9	...	6	4	341	0	5	5	9	7	8	9
...
1996	ljuryB4bfagHqV5FM9Ae	0	5	5	6	0	8	4	7	1	...	4	9	5	0	3	3	3	8	5	4
1997	lVracbzqACpwsUtnuHh	0	2	0	4	0	4	2	2	3	...	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	4	1	1
1998	LNAnljesrEDma5oUJVZI	0	7	6	5	0	3	3	5	5	...	7	2	4	0	2	3	5	6	3	5
1999	lolP1tiwELF9YNZQJSUO	0	7	4	6	0	5	3	7	2	...	5	6	5	0	7	3	4	6	2	5
2000	LQqA6FX02GWguYr1Zbe	0	1	1	2	0	4	1	1	0	...	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	1	0

2001 rows x 2001 columns

Figure 6: Top 2000 Bigram feature of Byte file

Out[29]:

ID	db ror	db dw	dd dw	db ror	dd db	dd dw	mov jmp	mov esi	push esi	...	db sub	xmm2 xmm2	test dw	lea rol	db edx	add xmm1	jmp ecx	xmm1 xmm2	xmm0 cmp	ebp dw
0	02IOCvYEy8mjuAQHax3	0	1	13	0	4	0	4	1	2	...	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
1	02mIBLHZTDFXGa7N6cr	0	88	6	0	463	0	5	10	7	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	03nJaQV6K2ObiCUmyWoR	1	3981	82	2	20110	4	19	7	21	...	7	0	5	0	2	0	3	0	0
3	04mcPSei852tgIKUwTJr	0	1	47	0	3	0	0	0	1	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	05LHG8R3iPn6aglo9z7	0	3195	95	4	17209	2	129	10	22	...	7	0	0	0	3	0	7	0	0
...
1996	ljuryB4bfagHqV5FM9Ae	0	2	29	0	33	0	0	15	24	...	1	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0
1997	lLvrcbzqACpwsUtmuHh	0	0	4	0	28	0	1	11	16	...	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1998	LNAInjestrEDma5oUUVZI	0	0	0	0	82	0	10	10	31	...	4	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
1999	lolP1thwELF9YNZQjSUO	0	0	23	0	26	0	0	12	13	...	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
2000	LOqA6FX02GWguYr11Zbe	2	0	0	0	62	1	5	0	25	...	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0

2001 rows x 501 columns

Figure 7: Top 500 Bigram feature of ASM file

Trigram analyzes the set of three characters or bytes. Trigram feature extraction of ASM file, makes the three pairs of vocabulary using countVectorizer and finds the frequency of each of the pairs, and selects the top 800 important features as shown in Figure 8 from the bigram feature using SelectKBest and chi-squared test.

Out[33]:

ID	db ror	dd dw	dd dw	db ror	dd ror	db db	db dw	dd dw	dw dw	...	esi eax edx	ebx edi esi	esi cmp edx	eax ecx ecx	esi edi ret	edx edi eax	push pop ebx	ecx edi eax	ecx edi ret	
0	02IOCvYEy8mjuAQHax3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	02mIBLHZTDFXGa7N6cr	0	3	3	0	195	85	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	03nJaQV6K2ObiCUmyWoR	1	10	14	2	0	12207	3969	4	1	...	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
3	04mcPSei852tgIKUwTJr	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0
4	05LHG8R3iPn6aglo9z7	0	16	43	1	3	8120	3166	1	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
...
1996	ljuryB4bfagHqV5FM9Ae	0	1	1	0	0	8	1	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1997	lLvrcbzqACpwsUtmuHh	0	0	1	0	0	9	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1998	LNAInjestrEDma5oUUVZI	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1999	lolP1thwELF9YNZQjSUO	0	0	2	0	0	4	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2000	LOqA6FX02GWguYr11Zbe	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

2001 rows x 801 columns

Figure 8: Top 800 Trigram feature of ASM file

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Random Forest

Random Forest Classifier is an ensemble machine learning algorithm that builds multiple decision trees on different samples and takes the majority vote of the output for classification [3]. Random Forest Classifier model is evaluated for performance using a

range of values for the hyper-parameter alpha (number of estimators), and the best value of alpha is chosen to predict the lowest log loss on the test and cross-validation set. Here, we define alpha values, i.e., 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500, and 3000. After creating a Random Forest Classifier with n_estimators equivalent to the current value of alpha, the code loops through each value of alpha. Finally, it trains the model using the training set. The algorithm then uses the trained model to determine the predicted probabilities of the target variable for the training, cross-validation, and test sets and find the log loss value(as shown in Figure 9) for the training, cross-validation, and test set.

```

For n_estimators=10, Train Log Loss=0.0446, CV Log Loss=0.4688, Test Log Loss=0.4845
For n_estimators=50, Train Log Loss=0.0448, CV Log Loss=0.1677, Test Log Loss=0.1646
For n_estimators=100, Train Log Loss=0.0433, CV Log Loss=0.1682, Test Log Loss=0.1594
For n_estimators=500, Train Log Loss=0.0424, CV Log Loss=0.1664, Test Log Loss=0.1598
For n_estimators=1000, Train Log Loss=0.0419, CV Log Loss=0.1673, Test Log Loss=0.1587
For n_estimators=1500, Train Log Loss=0.0422, CV Log Loss=0.1671, Test Log Loss=0.1599
For n_estimators=2000, Train Log Loss=0.0421, CV Log Loss=0.1667, Test Log Loss=0.1602
For n_estimators=2500, Train Log Loss=0.0422, CV Log Loss=0.1665, Test Log Loss=0.1603
For n_estimators=3000, Train Log Loss=0.0422, CV Log Loss=0.1666, Test Log Loss=0.1602

```

Figure 9: Log-loss of Random Forest

3.2. *K-Nearest Neighbor*

K Nearest Neighbor is a simple algorithm that stores all the available cases and classifies the new data or case based on a similarity measure. It is mainly used to classify a data point based on how its neighbors are classified [2]. Using the KNN algorithm, the training set's K nearest observations are located, and the new observation's class is determined through which of its K closest neighbors it occurs the most frequently. K is a hyper-parameter that the user has to select; its value usually depends on the dataset. Different distance metrics, such as the Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, or Minkowski distance, can be used to determine the distance between two data points. Once the distances have been computed, the K-nearest neighbors can be found, and the most prevalent class among these neighbors is designated as the predicted class for the new observation.

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model is evaluated for performance using a range of values for the hyper-parameter alpha, and the best value of alpha is chosen to produce the lowest log loss on the test and cross-validation set. Here, we define a range of alpha values, from 2 to 19, in increments of 2. After creating a KNN classifier with k neighbors equivalent to the current value of alpha, the code loops through each value of alpha. Finally, it trains the model using the training set. The algorithm then uses the trained model to determine the predicted probabilities of the target variable for the training, cross-validation, and test sets and find the log loss value for the training, cross-validation, and test set as shown in Figure 10.

```

For n_estimators=2, Train Log Loss=0.0043, CV Log Loss=0.2397, Test Log Loss=0.1086
For n_estimators=4, Train Log Loss=0.0252, CV Log Loss=0.2763, Test Log Loss=0.1388
For n_estimators=6, Train Log Loss=0.0461, CV Log Loss=0.2010, Test Log Loss=0.0847
For n_estimators=8, Train Log Loss=0.0647, CV Log Loss=0.2234, Test Log Loss=0.1059
For n_estimators=10, Train Log Loss=0.0812, CV Log Loss=0.2413, Test Log Loss=0.1261
For n_estimators=12, Train Log Loss=0.0947, CV Log Loss=0.2583, Test Log Loss=0.1426
For n_estimators=14, Train Log Loss=0.1062, CV Log Loss=0.2724, Test Log Loss=0.1552
For n_estimators=16, Train Log Loss=0.1168, CV Log Loss=0.2849, Test Log Loss=0.1687
For n_estimators=18, Train Log Loss=0.1264, CV Log Loss=0.2965, Test Log Loss=0.1786

```

Figure 10: Log-loss of K-Nearest Neighbor

3.3. XGBoost

The ensemble machine learning approach XGBoost, which is decision-tree based, uses the gradient boosting framework [4]. This technique generates decision trees in a sequential manner. Each independent variable is given a weight before being fed into the decision tree that predicts results. The weight of variables that the tree incorrectly anticipated is increased and these variables are subsequently supplied to the second decision tree. The final output is then combined to create a robust and accurate model [5].

The XGBoost model is evaluated for performance using a range of values for the hyperparameter alpha (number of estimators), and the best value of alpha is chosen to predict the lowest log loss on the test and cross-validation set. Here, we define alpha values, i.e., 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500, and 3000. After creating an XGBoost classifier with n_estimators equivalent to the current value of alpha, the code loops through each value of alpha. Finally, it trains the model using the training set. The algorithm then uses the trained model to determine the predicted probabilities of the target variable for the training, cross-validation, and test sets and find the log loss value for the training, cross-validation, and test set as shown in Figure 11.

```

For n_estimators=10, Train Log Loss=0.0667, CV Log Loss=4.1794, Test Log Loss=4.2007
For n_estimators=50, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8610, Test Log Loss=6.8802
For n_estimators=100, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8628, Test Log Loss=6.8820
For n_estimators=500, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8628, Test Log Loss=6.8820
For n_estimators=1000, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8628, Test Log Loss=6.8820
For n_estimators=1500, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8628, Test Log Loss=6.8820
For n_estimators=2000, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8628, Test Log Loss=6.8820
For n_estimators=2500, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8628, Test Log Loss=6.8820
For n_estimators=3000, Train Log Loss=0.0033, CV Log Loss=6.8628, Test Log Loss=6.8820

```

Figure 11: Log-loss of XGBoost

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

We have compared Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbor and XGBoost models based on the overfitting and underfitting and minimum cross-validation log-loss value, and test log-loss value. To check for overfitting or underfitting, we need to analyze the difference between the training and cross-validation (CV) log loss. A large difference between the

two can indicate overfitting, while a small difference may indicate underfitting as shown in Figure12, Figure13 and Figure14 respectively.

Figure 12: Random Forest

Figure 13: K-Nearest Neighbor

Figure 14: XGBoost

Here we can see that in Random Forest there is a relatively very small difference so there is no overfitting and underfitting but in K-Nearest Neighbor and XGBoost there is the large difference so, there is overfitting in both of the algorithms.

Again, we have compared Minimum Cross-Validation log-loss value as shown in Figure 15 and Minimum Test log-loss value as shown in Figure 16

Figure 15: Minimum Cross-Validation log-loss value

Figure 16: Minimum Test log-loss value

Again we have compared the model based on the minimum cross-validation log-loss value and minimum test log-loss value. According to cross-validation log-loss value Random Forest algorithm gives the lowest value 0.1664 and according to the test log-loss value K-Nearest Neighbor algorithm gives the lowest value 0.0847.

After comparing these algorithms we come to the conclusion that the Random Forest

Classifier gives a better performance in comparison to K-Nearest Neighbor and XGBoost because Random Forest has the lowest cross-validation log-loss value and there is no sign of overfitting and underfitting as there is a relatively very small difference between train log-loss value data and cross-validation log-loss value.

Here, we have used 10,872 test data for the final prediction and find extract the feature of these data same as the feature that we have extracted for the model training i.e., calculating the file size of ASM file, and Byte files, Unigram feature extraction of ASM file and Byte file, Bigram feature of ASM file and Byte file and Trigram feature of ASM file. Now Random Forest performs better so, Random Forest Classifier is taken as the model for the final prediction as shown n Figure 17.

ID	Class	
0	ITSUPtCmh7WdJcsYDwQ5	5
1	iwXK2bUysO0CPvBf8nTt	5
2	jEAbMPelkWmNgCrGU2QY	4
3	Jmo6elhLZ4t9r8QsxEg5	1
4	JtPFI4ewgdD78OzCMa3o	4
...
10867	zZpSmtquEKdTnYLQxC8a	2
10868	ZzQLhP9lqTGNkmc08nWb	4
10869	ZzSNKXrifA0xCFpHcQbG	2
10870	ZzunjPy0bdYmGpwfAagl	1
10871	zZWlaO7cSpK90g3vrqoD	4

10872 rows × 2 columns

Figure 17: Final Prediction

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This study presents an effective approach to malware classification using supervised machine learning techniques, targeting nine distinct malware families: Ramnit, Lollipop, Kelihos_ver3, Vundo, Simda, Tracur, Kelihos_ver1, Obfuscator.ACY, and Gatak. Given

the increasing sophistication and volume of malware threats in today's digital landscape, automated and accurate classification systems have become a critical necessity in cyber security.

The research demonstrates that meaningful features can be extracted from raw malware binaries through file size computation and n-gram sequence analysis. By applying SelectKBest with the chi-squared test, the most statistically significant features were retained while reducing dimensionality, making the models more efficient without sacrificing predictive power.

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Future Scope

While the current study establishes a strong foundation for malware classification using traditional machine learning techniques, several promising directions exist for future research and improvement. Future work could explore Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to automatically learn hierarchical features directly from raw byte sequences, potentially eliminating the need for manual feature engineering. Incorporating runtime behavioral features such as API call sequences, memory access patterns, registry modifications, and network traffic alongside static features could significantly improve classification accuracy, especially against obfuscated or polymorphic malware.

Training on larger, more diverse, and regularly updated datasets would improve the model's generalizability and robustness against newly emerging malware variants and zero-day threats. Future models should be tested and hardened against adversarial attacks, where malware authors deliberately manipulate binaries to evade ML-based detection systems. Optimizing the pipeline for real-time deployment in endpoint security systems would make the approach practically viable in production cyber security environments. Extending the classification framework beyond nine families to cover a broader and continuously evolving malware taxonomy would enhance its real-world applicability and scalability.

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